

The Impact of Customers' Trust and Satisfaction on Interest in Buying Clothes Online on Shopee at SMA Swasta Bina Guna Tanah Jawa

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Customers' trust, Satisfaction, Interest buying

Received : 8, September

Revised : 17, October

Accepted: 26, November

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ABSTRACT

The problem in this research is the low interest in buying clothing products online at Shopee at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School. This research aims to determine consumer trust and online consumer satisfaction with Shopee at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School. This type of research is quantitative research with a quantitative descriptive data analysis approach. The research population was students at the Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School with a total of 202 students. The research sample consisted of 120 students. The sampling technique used was random sampling by the researcher according to the class at school. The data collection technique used was a questionnaire. The hypothesis making technique uses multiple regression analysis and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The research results show that: 1) there is a positive and significant influence of consumer trust on buying interest. This can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of consumer trust (4.440) > t table value (1.65787) which means this variable is significant. 2) there is a positive and significant influence of consumer satisfaction on the positive influence of buying interest. This is found in the t test where the calculated t value of consumer satisfaction is (3.123) > the table value (1.65787) which means that this variable is significant. 3) consumer trust and consumer satisfaction together influence buying interest. This can be seen in the F test where the calculated F value (12.256) > table F value (3.07). The R square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.173, which means that 17.3% of the variables of consumer trust and consumer satisfaction influence the interest in buying clothing products online at Shopee at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School and the remaining 82.7% is the influence of other variables. not examined in this study.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern, practical era with the emergence of easy internet access which is becoming more and more sophisticated every year, we automatically present various variations of innovation and creativity via the internet network. Internet media is not just a communication medium, but is an inseparable part of the business world. With internet access, including social media, which is growing very widely every year, especially in the millennial era or now, traditional marketing systems are far behind or less effective for use as marketing media in business.

Starting from a barter system which was carried out by exchanging goods face to face, it developed into a sales system using a goods delivery process which facilitated buying and selling activities not only in the same location, then developed again through the internet network with a wider consumer reach. One application that is often used today is *Shopee*. *Shopee* was launched in 2015, *Shopee* is a platform tailored for each region and provides an easy, safe and fast online shopping experience for customers through strong payment and logistics support.

Business competition has become very tight and marketing has become very strong, marketing is the main key to a business or company running well. This causes many actors to market via the internet and generate sales, hence the emergence of e-commerce. There are many companies that provide ecommerce platforms. Iprice insights explains 47 e-commerce rankings in Indonesia in the 1st quarter. In 2020, *Shopee* was ranked first as the most popular among consumers in Indonesia.

However, there are a number of consumers who complain when submitting complaints, such as slow customer service response and lack of firmness in responding to complaints. This affects consumer confidence and consumer satisfaction where the delivery service chosen does not match the consumer's wishes and delivery costs become more expensive than before.

Apart from that, providing guarantees or guarantees from companies or marketers (such as: exchanging or replacing goods because they are damaged, servicing damaged products after use) to consumers after purchasing the product will also contribute to the level of consumer trust. Mainly because buyers cannot meet face to face with sellers, so the trust system becomes the main capital in every online buying and selling transaction. Consumer satisfaction is a person's feeling that appears either happy or disappointed which arises from comparing the product's perceived performance or results against consumer expectations. If the performance meets expectations, then the consumer will feel satisfied and if it fails the consumer will feel disappointed.

In order to attract consumers' buying interest to visit and transact via their site, e-commerce companies must build high trust in potential buyers. At first, people were not familiar with it and made people feel curious about the existence of the *Shopee* application, so that it made them curious and expanded to *Shopee* users as a place to market products.

As happened in one of the schools that is classified as advanced, namely SMA Bina Guna Tanah Jawa. There are many students who access *Shopee*, especially high school students. This was explained by Mr. Sampetua Sitohang, S.Pd as the principal at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School, that there were 202 students in the class. The student admitted that he had accessed the *Shopee* application.

High school students are one place where students are more aware of news developments and more sensitive to social media, which means students are very close to smartphones/gadgets, apart from that, students are in the age range of 15-18 years,

which is the number that corresponds to the age that uses them the most. smartphones/other gadgets.

Based on these problems, researchers are interested in taking the title "The Influence of Consumer Trust and Consumer Satisfaction on Interest in Buying Clothes Online on Shopee at Bina Guna Tanah Java Private High School".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Consumer Confidence

Popi Consumer Beliefs are all the knowledge possessed by consumers and all the conclusions consumers make about objects, attributes and benefits. student. According to Mowen and Minor (2013: 201) consumer trust is all the knowledge that consumers have about objects, attributes and benefits. Objects can be products, people, companies and anything about which someone has beliefs and attitudes.

Based on the definition of trust above, it can be concluded that trust is an individual's thoughts in carrying out cooperative relationships with certain parties, so that a good cooperative relationship is formed in the long term. And the importance of consumer knowledge regarding trust in a product regarding an attribute and the benefits of these various attributes. Marketers also need to understand the attributes of a product that consumers know and which attributes will be used to evaluate a product. Consumer confidence in a product, attributes and product benefits describe consumer perceptions.

2. Consumer Satisfaction

According to Febrini, PA, & Anwar (2019:38) customer satisfaction occurs when customer expectations match or can be met by performance or are close to being met and can even exceed customer expectations. Customer dissatisfaction can occur if the performance obtained is less than expectations, and customer satisfaction can occur if the performance obtained meets their expectations, feelings of very satisfaction and happiness can occur if the performance obtained by customers exceeds what they expected . Satisfaction can be achieved with a simple process, or with a complex, detailed process. In order to know the level of customer satisfaction, you must know everything that can cause satisfaction.

3. Purchase Interest

Purchase interest is something related to consumers' plans to buy certain products, as well as the number of product units needed in a certain period. Interest is described as a person's situation before an action, which can be used as a basis for predicting that behavior or action. Anwar & Adidarma (2016: 158) conclude that what is meant by consumer buying interest is a process of planning the purchase of a product that will be carried out by consumers by considering several things, including the number of product units needed in a certain time period, brand, and consumer attitudes. in consuming the product.

METHODS

Quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods that are based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical with the aim of arriving at a hypothesis. set. This research is used to determine the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, where in this research there are two independent variables (X), namely: Consumer Trust (X1), Consumer Satisfaction (X2) and the dependent variable is Purchase Interest (Y).

The location of this research was at Bina Guna Tanah Java Private High School. This research was carried out on high school students for the 2022/2023 academic year from May to September 2023 . The population in this study is Bina Guna Tanah Java Private High School students with a total of 202 students . The sample in this research was taken using the Slovin formula, where the sample in this research was 165 students.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Instrument Validity Test

After the instrument test was carried out, the next thing the researcher did was tabulate the results of the respondents' answers, namely by compiling answer codes and coding the data according to the classification of answers in table form. Tabulation of respondents' answers was carried out with the help of the Microsoft Excel program and using analytical data using analytical data in the SPSS 23 program. From the results of the calculations carried out you can determine whether or not the statement items in the research instrument are valid.

Items that are declared valid are items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.355 , while items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.355 are valid items . This can conclude that for the consumer trust questionnaire as many as 20 items that have a correlation value (r) > 0.355 as many as 17 and which have a correlation < 0.355 as many as 3 questions, for consumer satisfaction questionnaire questions A total of 17 questions had a correlation (r) > 0.355 and for the purchase interest questionnaire questions, there were 17 questions that were > 0.355 or valid questionnaire questions and 3 questionnaire questions that were < 0.355 or invalid. So if the questionnaire is < 0.355 or invalid , it is known that 51 questionnaire questions have data > 0.355 or valid data and 9 questionnaire items are invalid. Therefore, invalid questions are not used for further research

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the question is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained, it is known that *the Cronbach Alpha* obtained by consumer confidence is $0.779 > 0.60$, consumer satisfaction is $0.822 > 0.60$, and purchase interest is $0.787 > 0.60$. From the results of calculating consumer confidence, consumer satisfaction and purchasing interest, it can be concluded that the research instruments used are reliable.

Test Data Analysis Techniques

Based on the test results seen in Figure 1 , the p-plot graph shows the conclusion that the data is spread around the diagonal line, so the data is declared normal.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 1. Multicollinearity Test Results
Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	20,434	8,403		2,432	.017		
Consumer confidence	,380	,085	,383	4,440	,000	,951	1,052
consumer satisfaction	,264	,085	,269	3,123	,002	,951	1,052

a. Dependent Variable: buying interest

The assumption of Tolerance and Inflation (VIF) can be stated that if VIF > 10 and Tolerance value < 0.10 then multicollinearity occurs and if VIF <10 and Tolerance value > 0.10 then multicollinearity does not occur based on table 4.7 that Tolerance > 0.10 and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 2 Scatter Plot Curve

Based on Figure 4.3, it can be seen that the points spread above and below the number 0 on Y. Thus it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Hypothesis testing

Multiple Linear Regression Test

The purpose of the multiple regression analysis test is to determine the direction and how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Table 2. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results Coefficients ^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	20,434	8,403		2,432	,017
Consumer confidence	,380	,085	,383	4,440	,000
Consumer satisfaction	,264	,085	,269	3,123	,002

a. Dependent Variable: purchase interest

Based on table 2 , it is known that the value of constant (a) is 20.434, while the value of consumer trust (b1) is 0.380 and the value of consumer satisfaction (2) is 0.264, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_n X_n + e$$

$$Y = 20.434 + 0.380X_1 + 0.264 X_2 + 8.403$$

1. A constant of 20.434 means that the consistent value of the Buying Interest variable is 20.2434
2. The regression coefficient X1 is 0.380 and X2 is 0.264. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variables X1 and Variable X2 on Y is positive.

Partial Hypothesis Test (t)

The t test is used to find out whether what is used is accepted or rejected with a confidence level of 95% or =5% with the following conditions:

1. If $t_{count} > t_{table}$ with a significant value < 0.05 then the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable.
2. If $t_{count} < t_{table}$ with a significant value > 0.05 , then the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable.

**Table 3. Test results
Coefficients^a**

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	20,434	8,403		2,432	.017
Consumer confidence	,380	,085	,383	4,440	,000
Consumer satisfaction	,264	,085	,269	3,123	,002

a. Dependent Variable: buying interest

Based on table 3 , the tcount value and consumer trust (4.440) is greater than ttable (1.65787) and the tcount value of consumer satisfaction (3.123) is greater than ttable (1.65787). Thus, the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable.

Simultaneous Hypothesis Test (F)

The F test is carried out to find out whether the independent variables together have an influence on the dependent variable. In this case, Fcount is compared with Ftable with the following conditions:

1. If $F_{count} > F_{table}$ with a significant value < 0.05 , then H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted.
2. If $F_{count} < F_{table}$ with a significant value > 0.05 , then H_1 is rejected and H_0 is rejected.

**Table 4. F Test Results
ANOVA^a**

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2035.267	2	1017.633	12,256	,000 ^b
	Residual	9714.433	117	83,029		
	Total	11749.700	119			

a. Dependent Variable: purchase interest

b. Predictors: (Constant), consumer satisfaction, consumer trust

Based on table 4 It was found that the Fcount value (12.256) was greater than the Ftable value (3.07) . This indicates that the research results reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Thus, consumer trust and consumer satisfaction simultaneously influence the buying

interest variable at Bina Guna Private High School, Tanah Jawa with a significant level of influence. This gives meaning to the hypothesis which states that consumer trust and consumer satisfaction simultaneously influence the buying interest variable at Bina Guna Private High School. Java land is acceptable.

Coefficient of Determination Test

**Table 5. Coefficient of Determination Test Results
Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.416 ^a	.173	.159	9,112

a. Predictors: (Constant), consumer satisfaction, consumer trust

The R Square coefficient of determination value in table 5 is known to be 0.173 , which means that 17.3% of the consumer trust and consumer satisfaction variables influence purchasing interest at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School. Meanwhile, 82.7% is the influence of other variables not examined in the research.

The results of the analysis above have the implication that high consumer confidence and good satisfaction need to be taken into account in order to increase purchasing interest at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School. This is important in order to increase the variables of consumer trust and consumer satisfaction by 17.3%.

Discussion

The results of the classical assumption test, the above normality test are the main requirements to be able to proceed to the multiple regression analysis test with the data having a normal distribution and a significance level of > 0.05. In the consumer trust variable, Consumer Satisfaction and Purchase Interest have a normal distribution between variables with a significance level of 0.053 > 0.05, and based on Figure 1 the normal p-plot curve can be seen that the distribution of data is around the diagonal line and follows the diagonal direction, so standardized values and meet normality assumptions.

The results of the multicollinearity test show that Tolerance > 0.10 and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10, based on table 1 it is known that the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value is 1.052 < 10 and the Tolerance value is 0.951 > 0.10, so it can be concluded that the data does not have symptoms. multicollinearity.

The results of the heteroscedasticity test based on Figure 2 show that the dots spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. Thus it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur, and based on table 4.8 it is known that the significant value of consumer trust is (0.482) and the significant value of consumer satisfaction (0.641) it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity because the significance value must be greater than 0.05.

Based on table 2 , it is known that the value of constant (a) is 20.434, while the value of consumer trust (b1) is 0.411 and the value of consumer satisfaction (2) is 0.264, so the regression equation is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y &= \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_n X_n + e \\
 &= 20.434 + 0.380X_1 + 0.264X_2 + 8.403
 \end{aligned}$$

A constant of 20.434 means that the consistent value of the consumer satisfaction variable is 20.434. The regression coefficient X1 is 0.380 and X2 is 0.264. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variables X1 and Variable X2 on Y is positive.

The t test results are based on table 3. The calculated t value of consumer trust (4.440) is greater than the t table (1.65787). Based on the results obtained, H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted for the consumer trust variable. Thus, partially consumer satisfaction influences purchasing interest at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School, and the t-count value of consumer satisfaction (3.123) is greater than t table (1.65787). Based on the results obtained, H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted for the consumer satisfaction variable. Thus, partially consumer satisfaction influences purchasing interest at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School.

Partially, the consumer trust variable has a more dominant influence than consumer satisfaction. This can be seen from table 3 where the consumer trust value has the highest value, namely 4.440. This means that the consumer trust variable has more influence in increasing buying interest at Bina Guna Tabah Jawa Private High School than consumer satisfaction.

The F test results based on table 4 show that the Fcount value (12.256) is greater than the Ftable value (3.07). This indicates that the research results reject H0 and accept H1. Thus, simultaneously consumer trust and consumer satisfaction influence the variable interest in buying clothing products online at Shopee at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School with a significant level of influence.

The R Square coefficient of determination value in table 4.13 is known to be 0.173. Which means that 17.3% of the consumer trust and consumer satisfaction variables influence purchasing interest at Bina Guna Tabah Jawa Private High School. Meanwhile, 82.7% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the research and discussion described in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is a positive and significant influence of consumer trust on buying interest. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of consumer trust (4.440) > t table value (1.65787) which means this variable is significant.
2. There is a positive and significant influence of consumer satisfaction on buying interest. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of consumer satisfaction is (3.123) > t table (1.65787) which means this variable is significant.
3. Consumer trust and consumer satisfaction together influence purchasing interest. This result can be seen in the F test where the Fcount value (12.256) > Ftable value (3.07). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.173, which means that 17.3% of consumer trust and consumer satisfaction variables influence purchasing interest at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School and the remaining 82.7% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

FURTHER STUDY

As part of the conclusion of this research, the researcher provides the following suggestions:

1. Consumer trust and consumer satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on purchasing interest at Bina Guna Tanah Jawa Private High School. Therefore, to increase buying interest, you should pay attention to these two factors. Consumer trust, such as time discipline, needs to be considered by producers, especially in packaging products. This is very helpful in increasing buying interest. Apart from trust, satisfaction is also very helpful in increasing buying interest. Consumer satisfaction is also very influential in increasing buying interest, with high buying interest then sales activities can run well.
2. For future researchers to use other variables that influence buying interest. If in the future someone does similar research, they should do it in a different place, add the research variables and adjust the time to the period of the research being carried out.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author realizes that in writing this thesis, there are still many shortcomings. For this reason, with all humility the author hopes for suggestions and constructive criticism for the perfection of writing this thesis research proposal in the future so that it can provide direction to the author in the next steps of writing.

REFERENCES

- Angga Aptaguna, EP (2016). The Influence of Service Quality and Price on Intention to Purchase Go-Jek Services. *Jaya University Development* .
- Anwar, R. &. (2016). The Influence of Trust and Risk on Online Shopping Purchase Interest. *Sriwijaya Management and Business* , 155-168.
- Chrusnah, KT (1 December 2020). The Influence of Convenience and Security on Fintech Consumer Satisfaction. *Economics and Business* , 111-122.
- Darno, SY (1 November 2022). The Influence of Service Quality and Trust on Customer Satisfaction of Tokopedia Users in East Jakarta. *Innovative Management Students* , 1-50.
- Dr. Nila Nurochani, SM (2023). *Sharia E-Banking Service Development Strategy*. Jl. Jemurwonosari 1/39, Wonocolo, Surabaya: Cipta Media Nusantara (CMN).

- Erfan, M. (nd). The Effect of Plyometric Training (Pullover Toss) on Results (Throw IN) in Football Games. *Postgraduate sports education at Malang State University* .
- Erfan, M. (nd). Effects of Plyometric Training 9.
- Errie Margery, A. (January 1, 2018). Consumer Loyalty Using Generation Z Go-Jek Transportation in Medan City. *Management STIE Professional Management College Indonesia* .
- Fina Nailul Izzah, AM (1 January 2022). Intensity of Consumer Trust, Brand Image and Consumer Satisfaction on Chatime Customer Loyalty at Ciputra Mall Semarang. *Business Communication and Management* , 1-59.
- Indrasari, DM (2019). *Marketing And Customer Satisfaction*. Jl. Semolowaru No 84, Surabaya 60283 East Java: IKAPI No. 227/Extraordinary Member/JTI/2019.
- Irma Yanti Febrini, RW (2019). THE INFLUENCE OF EXPERIENTIAL MARKETING ON CONSUMER SATISFACTION AND REPURCHASE INTENTION AT KOPI WARUNG KLOTOK, KALIURANG, YOGYAKARTA. *Business Management* , 50-65.
- Mochamad Ridwan, TM (2020). HOW DO TRUST AND QUALITY OF INFORMATION AFFECT BUYING INTEREST AND PURCHASING DECISIONS? (study on Shopee customers in Samarinda). 1-10.
- Nyoman Ayu Nidya Larasati Dewi, AA (9 November 2019). The Role of Satisfaction in Mediating Shopping Experience on Repurchase Intention. *Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University (Unud) Bali, Indonesia* .
- Prisca Dwi Ratna Sari, AS (2020). The Influence of Brand Image, Price, and Service Quality on Interest in Buying Fashion Products Online in Jakarta (Study on the Zalora Online Shopping Site). *Veteran National Development University Jakarta* , 727-738.
- Riski Rosdiana, IA (2019). The Influence of Consumer Trust on Interest in Buying Clothing Products Online. *Economic Education, Ganesha Singaraja Education University, Indonesia* , 318-328.

- Riski Rosdiana, IA (2019). THE INFLUENCE OF CONSUMER TRUST ON INTEREST IN BUYING APPEARANCE PRODUCTS ONLINE. *Undiksha Economic Education* .
- Rosdiana, RI (2019). The Influence of Consumer Trust on Interest in Buying Clothing Products Online. *Undiksha Economic Education* , 318.
- Rosihan Anwar, WA (2016). The Influence of Trust and Risk on Online Shopping Purchase Interest. *Sriwijaya Management and Business* .
- Siahaan, WN (2021). The Influence of Consumer Confidence and Trust on Purchase Interest on the Lazada Online Shopping Site in Batam. *Management of the Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities* , 1-52.
- UTAMA, ID, & KUSUMA, AA (11 November 2019). The Influence of Customer Satisfaction in Mediating the Effect of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty. *Management* , 6468-4687.
- Z. Zulhelmi, a. S. (2018). ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF PRODUCT INNOVATION, PERCEPTION OF PRICE AND PRODUCT QUALITY ON PRODUCT TRUST THAT INFLUENCES CONSUMER PURCHASING DECISIONS (Case Study on "Atala Art" in Jepara). *Diponegoro Journal of Management* .